

Phraseologisms as a Tool For Creating an Artistic Image in Russian and Uzbek Literature

Mirzayunusova Z. I.

Senior Lecturer Kokand State Pedagogical Institute

Urinova Aziza

Master's student SOP 2nd year

Article information:

Manuscript received: 4 Aug 2024; **Accepted:** 4 Sep 2024; **Published:** 30 Oct 2024

Abstract: This research work is devoted to the study of the role of phraseological units in the creation of vivid literary images in Russian and Uzbek literature. It demonstrates how phraseological units, going beyond simple lexical substitution, become a powerful tool in the hands of authors for creating multifaceted characters, enriching the depth of the narrative, and enhancing the imagery and emotional coloring of works.

The paper analyzes the use of phraseological units in achieving vivid imagery, conveying subtle emotional nuances and forming national coloring in both Russian and Uzbek literary works. Specific examples from the works of famous authors such as Leo Tolstoy, Anton Chekhov, Fyodor Dostoevsky, Ch. Khait, A. Kodiriy and U. Khoshimov are given, demonstrating the versatility of phraseological units in forming literary style and influencing the reader's perception.

Keywords: Phraseology, artistic image, Russian literature, Uzbek literature, national color, emotional nuances, character development, literary analysis.

Introduction. Phraseologisms, which are stable word combinations with idiomatic meaning, play a significant role in fiction, going beyond simple lexical content. Their use allows writers and poets to create vivid artistic images, to give works depth, imagery and emotional richness. Catchphrases cannot fly literally, but with their figurative flight they make our speech more interesting and dynamic. We do not invent phraseologisms in the process of dialogue, but take them from language memory, like ready-made bricks for building figurative and expressive speech. That is why it is important to read a lot of fiction during student years in order to replenish vocabulary and phraseological stock.

Phraseologisms make our speech figurative and lively, they help to convey more meaning and do it emotionally and expressively. Phraseology plays an incomparable role in reflecting the national spirit expressed in the language of fiction. Proverbs, sayings and idioms that are part of phraseologisms, created and improved by the people over the centuries, became a rich heritage for the younger generation. Proverbs, being one of the genres of oral folklore that have a short form, but deep content, were created on the basis of centuries-old life observations of the people, socio-economic, political and cultural experience. Proverbs, according to their social, ideological tasks, become an expression of the worldviews of mainly the broad masses of the people, and in some cases a certain social stratum or group. For this reason, the thematic

scope of proverbs is very extensive, and it will be impossible to limit this scope within the limits of insignificant life reality, and in this regard, there is not a single sphere of social life that would not find its vivid reflection in proverbs.

Methodological basis for studying the topic. Currently, there are studies describing phraseological units with somatisms, cosmonyms, zoonyms. Phraseologists in their works are engaged in identifying the symbolic content of key components, recreating the linguistic picture of the world, identifying interlingual parallels, and studying the linguacultural values of phraseological units.

The development of phraseology occurs on the material of languages. Thus, the issues of phraseology were studied by N.N. Amosova, A.V. Alefirenko, V.L. Arkhangelsky, Sh. Bally, V.V. Vinogradov, M.M. Kopylenko, A.V. Kunin, B.A. Larin, A.I. Molotkov, A.I. Smirnitsky, V.N. Teliya, N.M. Shansky.

The axiological aspect of phraseological units in the field of regional studies was described by E.M. Vereshchagin, V.G. Kostomarov, Yu.E. Prokhorov, V.N. Teliya, V.M. Shaklein and others.

The development of methodological recommendations and systems of exercises for their implementation in teaching foreign speakers of certain nationalities was carried out by E.S. Korobaynikova, A.S. Miloslavsky, L.G. Pomozova, N.M. Rumyantseva, A.P. Soboleva, G.D. Tomakhin and others.

The necessity of introducing phraseological units into the linguistic content of the educational process is described in the works of A.N. Vasiliev, L.A. Voinov, N.N. Kokhtev, O.A. Lapteva, O.D. Mitrofanov, E.I. Motina and others. Methods of presenting phraseological material and methodological organization for training are reflected in the works of M.L. Basko, E.A. Bystrova, G.A. Velichko, V.I. Zimin, E.E. Minakova, I.N. Uspensky, T.P. Chepkova, N.M. Shansky and others.

Analysis of the use of phraseological units in fiction

In works of Russian and Uzbek literature, phraseological units demonstrate their multifaceted role in the creation of an artistic image, which helps to better understand the content of the image:

1. Creating vivid images:

Phraseologisms, like miniature paintings, enliven the text, creating memorable images. For example, "to twiddle one's thumbs" paints an image of a lazy person, "to pound water in a mortar" - an image of useless work, and "to throw dust in the eyes" - an image of cunning and deception. Such figurative use of phraseologisms makes the text more visual and allows the author to convey his thoughts and feelings more accurately.

2. Conveying subtle shades of emotion:

Phraseologisms have great emotional power and are able to convey a variety of feelings that are difficult to express in simple words. "To burn with shame" is not just shame, but disgrace, "the soul sank into the heels" is not just fright, but strong fear, "to shake a fist" is not just aggression, but anger that is ready to grow into action.

3. Creation of national color:

Phraseological units capture the history of the people, their traditions, and mentality. "Roll up your sleeves" is an active, energetic action, "to slap hands" is a quick, decisive agreement, "to lead by the nose" is a cunning deception. The use of such expressions gives the works a national specificity, allowing the reader to better understand the lifestyle, values, and character of the heroes.

Examples of the use of phraseological units in Russian literature:

L.N. Tolstoy: In "War and Peace" (1869) the phraseological unit "to twiddle one's thumbs" characterizes the idle lifestyle of Pierre Bezukhov during his period of idleness and spiritual emptiness.

A.P. Chekhov: In the story "Ionych" (1898), the phraseological unit "to pound water in a mortar" emphasizes the meaninglessness of the life of the main character, Ivan Dmitrievich Startsev, who, despite his intellectual abilities, cannot find a place for himself in life.

F.M. Dostoevsky: In the novel "Crime and Punishment" (1866), the phraseological unit "to play cat and mouse" symbolizes the tense atmosphere of Raskolnikov's psychological struggle with himself, his constant attempts to deceive himself and those around him.

Examples of the use of phraseological units in Uzbek literature:

Ch. Khayit: In the novel "Ota Yurt" (1960) the phraseological unit "tosh" "Botir" (stone hero) symbolizes the strength and resilience of the Uzbek people, their ability to withstand any difficulties.

A. Kodiriy: In the novel "O'tkan kunlar" (1926) idiom "kul Ustiga r ulim" (hand on hand) conveys the feeling of hopelessness and despair of the main character, Otabek, who finds himself in a hopeless situation, forced to put up with injustice and oppression.

U. Khoshimov: In the novel "Osmon manzarasi" (1973) phraseological unit "kuz" "ochib-yumgunda" (in the blink of an eye) emphasizes the transience of time and the fragility of human life, which is especially important in the context of the story being told, where the characters face tragic events.

Conclusion: As a result of the conducted research, it would be appropriate to assert that phraseological units, being diverse in ideological content, spiritual and moral result, have characteristic features in their stylistic function. In connection with the similarity of the law of thinking in all nations and the existence of beliefs and ideas close to each other, even in languages differing in structure, the same or close in meaning proverbs and sayings can be created.

Phraseologisms are not just elements of language, they are a powerful tool that allows authors to create artistic images, enrich prose and poetic texts, making them deeper, more figurative and emotional. The use of phraseologisms gives works a national specificity, allows the reader to better understand the world of the heroes and be imbued with their feelings.

Bibliography:

1. N. M. Shansky, On phraseological unit as a linguistic unit and subject of phraseology Moscow 1985
2. Kuznetsova E.V. "Phraseologisms in artistic speech" (2000)
3. Ibragimovna, M. Z. (2023). Stages of translation development in Uzbekistan. *Boletin de Literatura Oral-The Literary Journal*, 10 (1), 2595-2604.
4. Mirzayunusova, Z. I. (2024). THE ROLE OF VOCABULARY WORK IN THE SPEECH DEVELOPMENT OF FOREIGN PHONE STUDENTS IN A MODERN SCHOOL ENVIRONMENT. *FAN, TA'LIM, MADANIYAT VA INNOVATSIYA JURNALI | JOURNAL OF SCIENCE, EDUCATION, CULTURE AND INNOVATION*, 3 (6), 173-178.